

DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE SOCIAL WORKERS ON THE BASIS OF ACMEOLOGICAL APPROACH

Mirzajanov Jamshid Kaharjan ugli

Independent researcher of Fergana State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11058171>

Annotation: the thoughts on developing the intelligence and abilities of future social workers and acmeological development of their professional competence are analyzed. In addition, the socio-pedagogical factors of acquiring knowledge and skills in improving the pedagogical skills of a social worker are analyzed.

Key words: acmeological, individual capabilities, ability, pedagogy, heuristic creativity, competent approach

INTRODUCTION

Currently, the issue of studying the professional development of a person, professional abilities and the level of competence poses specific tasks for a number of fields of pedagogy and psychology. Because, in the acmeological development of a person, his professional development also has an important place. Socio-psychological competence, which is the subject of our research, and its development is a unique complex process. A similar concept is expressed in all scientific literature, but without denying this concept, it can be said that a single scientific methodological development of a perfect level has not yet been adopted to analyze the efficiency of professional activity only as a criterion of socio-psychological efficiency as a means of competence.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The concepts of competence and competence are presented in the scientific works of scientists such as I.V.Petrova, YE.V.Sadon, O.YE.Gavrilova, A.V.Tarasova [4]. Also, in the UNESCO concept "The competent teacher 2010-2020", the modern interpretation of the concept of competence and its practical importance are highlighted [5].

Aspects of education of professional competences of specialists by pedagogical scientists of Uzbekistan .Researched by Khoshimova [6].

A person's professional competence is a combination of knowledge, skills and abilities, and having the ability to foresee the results of pedagogical activities, he is responsible for the results of his activities in front of society, pedagogues and psychologists [1].

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Ability characterizes the individual capabilities of a person. Under the same conditions, talented workers achieve more success in their activities than people with low abilities. The ability ensures that a person moves faster in both general and special development, achieves the highest results in executive and creative activities. A skilled person can quickly master a specialty and achieve a high level of skill and can innovate in production, science or culture[2]. Ability is different from knowledge. Knowledge is the result of scientific reading, and ability is a characteristic of a person's psychological and physiological structure. Ability is a prerequisite for learning, and at the same time, it is to some extent a product of learning. In the process of mastering general and special knowledge, as well as acquiring professional

skills, the ability is perfected and developed. Closer concepts to ability are skills and competencies. Skills are the perfect method of work performed on the basis of experience and knowledge gained during the professional activity of a teacher. Qualifications are a set of automated components of professional intellectual activity formed during the teacher's conscious activity. They are the processes that form the basis of the mechanism of the teacher's professional activity, which, together with the ability, ensure the achievement of pedagogical skills, as a result of which the teacher achieves great success in his professional activity. A capable but ignorant person cannot achieve much. Ability is manifested in skills and competencies. In fact, the skills and abilities of a talented person are multifaceted and perfected. Skills and abilities can partially compensate for a lack of ability or correct a lack of ability. Skills are generally called skills. Skill is also a derivative of ability. So, ability is formed in the process of emergence of skills and qualifications [3].

In pedagogy, the ability of a teacher is an opportunity, the necessary level of his skills improves only in the process of teaching and education and creates the basis for achieving success. Innate abilities are called intelligence. Talent, talent, genius are the stages of development of abilities achieved during the creative activity of a person. Abilities are qualities of a person, such as character, that exist only in certain activities.

In psychology, ability is a person's ability to acquire professional knowledge, skills, and abilities without difficulty and easily, and successfully engage in an activity. It is also evident in the teacher's professional activity.

The qualities of professional activity that determine the content of education are manifested in the creativity of a person. Creativity is qualitatively new, original and unrepeatable activity. Any problem identified in productive creativity is successfully resolved; These aspects are manifested in the main part of people who are capable of creativity.

Heuristic creativity refers to the bold assimilation and promotion of innovations related to professional activities taking place in society, that is, to intensify the process of generating ideas (hypotheses) on the basis of it and to consistently realize their closeness to reality (probability, reliability). Increase and the ability to act boldly in a new situation, development of thinking based on the thinking process is observed.

In creative creativity, a person creates new theories of social importance, comes up with his own thoughts and suggestions, only skilled and experienced, capable people can achieve this.

Natural anatomical-physiological ability targets form the physiological basis of abilities. The set of ability marks, which later turn into abilities, is called a person's talent.

People with special abilities successfully engage in certain activities only in their professional fields. A unique combination of abilities that ensures successful, independent and perfect performance of an activity is called talent [4].

Pedagogical ability in the profession of social work, as in all specialties, determines the characteristics of his personal talent and creates subjective conditions for the successful implementation of this type of professional activity. Any activity is complex and makes different demands on a person. If the system of personal characteristics can meet these requirements, a person can demonstrate his ability to successfully perform an activity, if any of the characteristics are not developed, a person is characterized as having low ability in relation to a certain type of work.

A person's ability is of great social and personal importance. Ability helps to ensure high labor productivity, consequently, rapid growth of social wealth in terms of quantity and quality,

development of society. That is why it is strictly necessary to open the intelligence and abilities of future social workers and learn to use them in their place. The ability to improve the pedagogical skills of a social worker ensures the acquisition of knowledge and the formation of skills.

Competent approach requires learners not to acquire knowledge and skills separately, but to acquire them as a whole. In connection with this demand, in turn, the system of choosing the content of education is changing. The selection and practical application of educational content in the training of future social workers, in turn, requires the improvement of competencies and functions that meet the requirements of the educational process.

In the training of social workers in higher education institutions, the content of education is understood as the clearly defined amount and scope of knowledge, skills, qualifications and general and professional competencies that students should acquire.

Common competencies for training future social workers:

- to have systematic knowledge related to the worldview, to know the basics of humanitarian and natural sciences, to know the current issues of the current state policy, to be able to independently analyze social problems and processes;
- to have a comprehensive idea of the processes and events taking place in nature and society:
- pedagogical design of the educational process in the electronic information educational environment;
- to have a competitive general professional training in the relevant bachelor's field of education, etc.[5].

Professional competencies in training future social workers:

- preparation for the use of knowledge of modern problems of science and education in solving general professional tasks, as well as acquiring the skills of creating and applying informational and didactic support for successful implementation;
- formation of technical and creative thinking, intellectual abilities;
- to be able to analyze the status, main directions and laws of the development of the education system in the global framework, to reveal the general views of national and specific features, the positive and negative aspects of the international pedagogical experience, to enrich the national pedagogical culture, to clarify its forms and methods;
- general secondary education consists of the development of aesthetic culture and creativity, self-development and self-care competence, communication, communicative and practical activity development, competence formation, etc. in schoolchildren.

There are no limited types of abilities of a social worker in pedagogical psychology. Types of pedagogical skills can increase and change depending on the development of science and society.

As a result of many years of scientific research and observations of scientists, the following main qualities of pedagogical ability have been distinguished:

1. Love for one's profession.
2. Good knowledge of his specialty, interest in it.
3. To have pedagogical tact (decency and beauty).
4. Being able to get absorbed in the team.
5. Creative approach to one's work.
6. Feeling responsible.
7. Acquiring educational knowledge.

Pedagogical abilities do not only express the effectiveness and conditions of pedagogical activity, but also the result of successful work in many ways.

Pedagogical scientist I.P. Podlasiy defined the structure of pedagogical ability as follows:

- 1) organization - uniting learners, planning their activities, involving them in team work, drawing conclusions;
- 2) diagnostic - to be able to choose the educational material, to be able to explain the educational material in an understandable, clear, descriptive, reliable and systematic way; stimulating the development of students' interest in learning and intelligence, increasing learning and learning activity, and developing critical thinking and creativity;
- 3) perceptive - influencing the inner world of learners; the ability to objectively assess their emotional state, to identify peculiarities in their psyche;
- 4) communicative - the ability to establish a relationship with students and the team aimed at the pedagogical goal;
- 5) suggestive (suggestion - persuasion) - emotional impact on students;
- 6) about research - the ability to understand and objectively evaluate pedagogical processes and situations;
- 7) related to scientific knowledge - the ability to acquire a certain amount of scientific knowledge related to the chosen specialty;
- 8) gnostic - the ability to study the object, process and the results of one's activity and correct it based on the obtained results [6].

Pedagogical scientist F.N. Gonobolin suggests dividing pedagogical skills into the following types:

- didactic skills;
- academic abilities;
- perceptive abilities;
- speech skills;
- organizational ability;
- authoritarian skills;
- communication skills;
- pedagogical imagination;
- the ability to divide attention [7].

The characteristics of a social worker related to mutual exchange of ideas play a key role in pedagogical ability. The main characteristics of the following pedagogical skills are continuously formed as a result of the high pedagogical and psychological knowledge of a social worker:

Communicative ability: understanding and sympathizing with the mental state of a person in the interaction with the community and parents, residents of the neighborhood, pure voluntariness in communication. A social worker should have psychological knowledge and regularly develop a culture of behavior.

CONCLUSION

The review of pedagogical and psychological literature shows that the communicative abilities of future social workers are manifested as a complex integrative phenomenon as professional skills that ensure the employee's communication with other participants of the work process, its continuous maintenance and development. In general, humanity has passed through several stages during its evolutionary development: "homo habilis" (business man), "homo potentis" (capable man), "homo sapiens" (intelligent man). Many researchers have suggested

that our time be called "homo loguens", that is, the speaking man. Because everyone is not excluded from the process of transmitting or receiving information, which, in turn, increases the importance of communicative activity. For example, V.A. Krutetsky defined the concept of a person's communicative ability as follows: communicative ability - the ability to communicate and establish communication, the ability to mingle with people, to find the right way to approach people, to have effective interactions with them the ability to establish, the presence of pedagogic-psychological sophistication..

References:

1. Vakhobov M.M. Improvement of the teaching quality monitoring model in the general secondary education system: Ped.fanl.dokt.dis. autoref. - Tashkent, 2016. - 81 p.
2. Davletshin M.G. Ability and its diagnosis. - T.: "Teacher", 1997. -134 p.
3. Khalikov A. Pedagogical skill. Study guide. - T.: "ECONOMICS", 2010. - P. 44.
4. Khalikov A. Pedagogical skills. Study guide. - T.: "ECONOMICS", 2010. - P. 48.
5. Kuliyeva Sh. Principles of choosing the content of education in the training of future teachers. "Pedagogical skill" scientific-theoretical and methodological magazine. 2023, No. 9. - P. 70.
6. Podlasiy V.P. Pedagogika. Uchebnik. - M.: "Visshye obrazovaniye", 2006. - 540 s.
7. Gonobolin F.N. O nekotorig psixicheskix kachestvax lichnosti uchitelya // J. Voprosi psixologii. - 1995. №1. - S. 100-111.

